

profile	German	English	description by Rotroff/Berlin/Hayes	notes + references
<p>PW 1</p>	<p>Tischamphore? Krug?</p>	<p>table amphora</p>	<p>medium-sized, two-handled jar with a base (rather than a toe) and a wide neck and mouth (Berlin)</p>	<p>B1</p>

<p>PW 24</p>		lagynos	table jugs with specific characteristics of a long, slim neck, vertical strap handle, and carinated or biconical body (Berlin)	B1
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<p>PW 38</p>	Krug Kanne	jug(BE) /pitcher (US)	single handled pouring vessels in a size and fabric suitable for serving (Berlin)	B1
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<p>PW 178</p>	<p>Kochtopf</p>	<p>cooking pot/stew pot</p>	<p>B: cooking pots: have globular bodies, with short necks and relatively narrow mouths; stew pots: deep, round bodies and wide mouths</p>	<p>B1</p>
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	<p>Kanne mit Ausguß</p>	<p>juglet</p>	<p>small , single handled pouring vessels (Berlin)</p> <p>Krug mit rundem Rand</p>	<p>B1</p>
	<p>Becher</p>	<p>beaker</p>	<p>tall cylindrical drinking cup, no foot</p>	<p>very plain form</p>

<p>PW 507</p>	Topf	jar	<p>Jar is an unwieldy category. Since the name does not encompass a single closely defined form or function, it is a catchall for a wide variety of shapes, both large and small. The one characteristic that all jars have in common is that they are closed vessels, which makes them appropriate as containers, for wet or dry goods. Some jars have more specific designations. The most obvious examples are amphorae, which are generally thought of as long-distance transport vessels. But many other vessels may be considered jars. (Berlin, p. 30)</p>	B
	Platte	platter	<p>no consensus when something is a platter; simply larger size than plate</p>	
<p>647</p>	Teller	plate	<p>Hayes: uses plate and dish synonymously</p>	<p>H dish – unclear what this means; preference would be just plate</p>

<p>PW 160</p>	Schale/Schüssel	saucer	saucer or deep plate; sometimes called plate but never as flat or shallow as that term implies (Rotroff)	R, B1, H profile from B1 small plate; shape not quite a bowl but not a plate either; Hayes refers to a type with two variants, D > 20cm – plate D < 20 cm - saucer
<p>PW 141</p>	Schale/Schüssel	bowl	bowls/cups are distinguished from saucers by narrower, deeper profiles	B1 differentiating between cup and bowl is difficult
<p>PW 163</p>	Deckel	saucer lid		B1
<p>PW 234</p>	Kasserolle	casserole	open cooking vessel, generally applied to shapes wider than they are tall; characteristics: lip shaped to carry a lid, rounded or angular body wall, more or less rounded bottom (Berlin)	B1
	Pfanne	pan/frying pan		

		cup		very confusing term; would avoid it
		dish		seldom; very confusing term; would avoid it

References:

English:

H = J. W. Hayes, Roman Pottery: Fine-Ware Imports, The Athenian Agora 32 (Princeton, NJ 2008).

B1 = L. Cornell – S. Herbert – A. Berlin – K. Warner Slane, Tel Anafa. II:1, The Hellenistic and Roman Pottery, Journal of Roman Archaeology. Supplementary Series 10:II,1 (Ann Arbor MI 1997).

B = A. Berlin, Naukratis/Kom Hadid: A Ceramic Typology for Hellenistic Lower Egypt, in: Leonard – Berlin (Hrsg.), Ancient Naukratis : excavations at a Greek emporium in Egypt. Part 2. The Excavations at Kom Hadid. AASOR 55 (Cambridge 2001) 26-163.

R = S. I. Rotroff, Hellenistic Pottery: Athenian and Imported Wheelmade Table Ware and Related Material, Athenian Agora 29 (Princeton N.J. 1997).

German:

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I. Bauer – B. Kerkhoff-Hader – W. Endres, Leitfaden zur Keramikbeschreibung (Mittelalter-Neuzeit) : Terminologie, Typologie, Technologie, Kataloge der Prähistorischen Staatssammlung 2 (Kallmünz/Opf. 1986).

N. Hofer – I. Gaisbauer – B. Österreich, Handbuch zur Terminologie der mittelalterlichen und neuzeitlichen Keramik in Österreich (Horn 2010).